

Effect of Price, Brand Image, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze and identify the effect of price, brand image, and trust both simultaneously and partially on customer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio at Arista Tajur. Questionnaires were distributed to 100 respondents who were taken by purposive sampling technique with criteria; consumers who have purchased Yamaha Mio motorbikes and consumers who are seen as mature enough to fill out the questionnaire, at least seventeen years old, the reason that they have been able to determine the satisfaction received rationally. The questionnaire was tested with validity tests, reliability tests, and also classic assumption tests. The results of these tests are valid, reliable, and can be used for regression data. The analytical method used in this study is a descriptive and verification method with a quantitative approach. The results of the study show that the variables of price, brand image, and trust simultaneously or partially have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio at Arista Tajur. The test results for the coefficient of determination (R Square) are 57.6% while the remaining is 42.4%. The relationship between price, brand image, and trust is very strong with a correlation coefficient of 0.759

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, business competition is increasingly competitive, which results in every company trying to be a winner in marketing its products. Motorcycle is a vehicle that can not be separated from the activities of both urban and rural communities. Especially at this time the cost of Transportation is getting more expensive, fuel consumption is limited by the government, as well as congestion that almost always adorns the streets of the city. For this reason, an alternative is needed to overcome this problem, so the proliferation of motorcycle industries in Indonesia. Motorcycle manufacturers must be aware of the needs and expectations of the Indonesian people who are diverse, need a reliable and effective product. The number of companies engaged in the same field, makes competition increasingly fierce. The intense competition among *dealer motorcycle* dealers encourages companies to find the right strategy so that the company can win the competition. One strategy to win the competition is to provide satisfaction to consumers.

According to Tjiptono (2016: 74), consumer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment of someone who appears after comparing the perception of the performance of a product and its expectations. One of the factors that affect consumer satisfaction is price. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2014: 345) price is the amount of money charged on a product or service or the amount of value exchanged by consumers for the benefits of owning or using the product or service. Brand image is also a factor that affects consumer satisfaction. According to Wijaya (2016: 204), brand image is knowledge, opinions from customers and non-physical characteristics and physical products, the image that customers give to the product. The next factor that affects consumer satisfaction is trust. According to Yee & Faziharudean (2010: 72), trust is a person's willingness to behave in a certain way because of the belief that *partner*-his partner will provide the satisfaction he expects and an expectation that a person generally has that the words, promises, or statements of others can be trusted.

Yamaha Arista Tajur is one of the motorcycle dealers located in the city of Bogor, where its business activities in addition to selling motorcycles also sell spare parts and *spare parts*. Adapun jenis merek motor Yamaha yang dijual adalah motor bebek (Jupiter dan Vega RR), *Matic* (NMAX, Mio, Vino dan Fazzio) serta motor *Sport* (GSX dan R15). Motor *Matic* is currently one of the favorite motorcycles for two-wheeled riders. Its presence is now starting to shift the position of motorcycles and *sports* that previously led the market share of motorcycle sales. AISI Data in 2021 Yamaha Mio occupied the second position in sales of *auto Matic motorcycles* in Indonesia.

(<https://tmcblog.com/2022/01/16/honda-kuasai-7768-pangsa-pasar-sepeda-motor2021-indonesia/>). however, Mio motorcycle sales at Arista Tajur dealers are inversely proportional to national sales. As an initial overview of the sale of Yamaha Mio motorcycles at Arista dealers can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Yamaha Mio Motorcycle Sales Data in Arista Tajur
Year 2021

Month	Sales Target (units)	Realization (units)	Target Achievement (%)	Description
January	15	10	67	Not Achieved
February	15	8	53	Not Achieved
March	15	8	53	Not Achieved
April	15	10	67	Not Achieved
May	15	7	47	Not Achieved
June	15	8	53	Not Achieved
July	15	10	67	Not Achieved
August	15	13	87	Not Achieved
September	15	16	107	Achieved
October	15	15	100	Achieved
November	15	17	113	Achieved
December	15	14	93	Not Achieved
Total	180	396	907	Not achieved
Average	15	11	75	Not achieved

Source: Yamaha Arista Tajur Bogor, 2022

Based on Table 1 Yamaha Arista Tajur motorcycle sales in 2021 tend to fluctuate. The average sales achievement is 75% of the sales target. The highest sales achievement occurred in September, October and November. In those months, motorcycle sales were quite high because of the motorcycle sales promotion activities carried out by Yamaha Arista Tajur such as, greek market, *door to door*, exhibitions and *event activities* as well as the distribution of brochures.

For the rest of the months have not reached the sales target. Failure to achieve the target can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Consumer Assessment of Satisfaction on Yamaha Mio Motorcycle in Arista Tajur

Indikator Consumer Satisfaction Indicator	Type of Complaint	Interpretation
Interest Revisit	Consumers feel the motor is not appropriate and has not	The vast majority (67%) stated that Yamaha Arista Tajur gives Yamaha Mio motorcycles that consumers feel are not satisfactory.

	been satisfactory.	
Total Consumer Complaints		20
Total Tanggapan Consumer Assumptions		30
Percentage of Total Complaints (%)		67%

Source: Preliminary Survey, 2022

Based on Table 2 states that the inaccessibility occurs because there are still complaints against the indicator of interest in revisiting. The average consumer assessment of consumer satisfaction with Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur shows from 30 consumer responses there are 20 consumers who complain or 67% with the type of consumer complaints feel the motor given is not appropriate and not satisfactory to make consumers feel no interest to visit again.

Based on another preliminary survey conducted on 30 people who have bought Yamaha Mio motorcycles, found indicators on prices that are still considered not in accordance with consumer expectations yatu on indicators of price conformity with benefits. Meanwhile, in the brand image indicator, there are indicators that are still considered less good, namely the indicator of brand association and Brand Excellence. And as for the last one, namely the indicator of trust, there are indicators that are still considered not in accordance with the indicator of integrity and goodness.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Marketing Management

Marketing management is the analysis, planning, implementation, and management of programs designed to create, establish, and maintain profitable exchanges with target markets to achieve organizational goals (Ismanto, 2020:20).

Customer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment of someone who appears after comparing the perception of the performance of a product and its expectations (Tjiptono, 2016:74). Indicators of consumer satisfaction are 1) the suitability of expectations; 2) interest in revisiting; 3) willingness to recommend. According to Tjiptono and Gregory (2016: 295), there are factors that affect consumer satisfaction including price, brand image, and trust.

Price

Price is the amount of money that must be spent by consumers to get the product or service they buy to meet the needs and desires of consumers. According to Tjiptono (2016: 218), states that price is the only element of the marketing mix that gets income or revenue for the company. Price indicators are

1) price affordability; 2) conformity of price with quality; 3) conformity of price with benefits; 4) price competitiveness.

Brand Image

Brand image also plays a role in consumer satisfaction, because the image of brand associated with consumer attitudes and beliefs to buy a product. According to Firmansyah (2019: 60) defining a brand is a name, term, sign, emblem or design, or a combination thereof to mark the products or services of one seller or group of sellers and to distinguish them from competitors. Brand image indicators are 1) brand identity; 2) brand personality; 3) brand association; 4) brand behavior.

Beliefs

Beliefs also become one of the factors of consumer satisfaction. Trust is the belief that a person will find what he wants in others, and what he is not afraid of. Yee & Faziharudean (2010: 113) states that trust is a person's willingness to behave in a certain way because of the belief that *partner*-his partner will provide the satisfaction he expects and an expectation that is generally owned by a person that the words, promises, or statements of others can be trusted. Indicators of trust are 1) integrity; 2) kind; 3) competence.

Effect of Price, Brand Image, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

In research, Putri Wulandari (2021) states that Price, brand image, and trust can have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. Similarly, research conducted by Nuel Simatupang & Sri Patmawati (2019) shows that Price, brand image, and trust simultaneously affect consumer satisfaction. H₁: There is a simultaneous positive and significant influence of Price, brand image, and trust on consumer satisfaction.

Effect of Price on Consumer Satisfaction

Price is the value exchanged to obtain a product or service. This will certainly determine the level of customer satisfaction. Pratama research (2020) states that consumer satisfaction is influenced by price, in which case it is argued that the more competitive the prices and benefits received from the products given are in accordance with consumer expectations, thus making consumer satisfaction increase.

H₂: There is a positive and significant effect of price on consumer satisfaction.

Influence of Brand Image on Consumer Satisfaction

Brand image is a perception that arises in the minds of consumers when remembering a brand of a particular product. According to research conducted by Sundari (2021) states that brand image variables have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

H₃: There is a positive and significant influence of brand image on consumer satisfaction.

Effect of Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

Trust is defined as all knowledge held by the consumer and all inferences made by the consumer about the object, its attributes and benefits. According to research conducted by Masfufah (2021) states that the EI trust variable has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. Likewise, the results of research conducted by Marlina Wijayanti (2021) state that the belief variable has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

H₄: there is a positive and significant effect of trust on consumer satisfaction.

METHODS

The objects of this study are price, brand image, trust and consumer satisfaction. The location of this study was conducted at Yamaha Arista Tajur Jalan Raya Tajur, Bogor, West Java 16720.

The population in this study is consumers who have bought Yamaha Mio at Arista Tajur, which amounted to 396 (based on sales data in 2021). While the sample in this research is as many as 100 respondents. This is based on the use of purposive sampling. With data retrieval techniques consisting of interviews, data retrieval using questionnaires, and also carried out on observation or observation.

The data testing method in this study is validity, reliability, and classical assumption tests and multiple linear regression analysis, which are carried out with the help of a software program *statistical package for the social sciences* (SPSS). Based on the results of testing the validity of the 30 respondents that the results of testing the validity of the variable price (X₁), brand image (X₂), Trust (X₃), and consumer satisfaction (Y), were declared valid because the R_{count} (3) R_{table}. Likewise, the reliability test results show that all variables used have a value of Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.6 so all variables can be declared reliable and acceptable.

The results of Uji the classical assumption test consist of the following :
Normality Test

The statistical test that can be used to test the residual normality is a nonparametric statistical test Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) significant level (3) 0.05. Normality test in this study using IBM SPSS 25. Here are the results of statistical analysis normality test:

Table 3. Test Results Normality

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.11495867
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.053
	Positive	.049
	Negative	-.053

Test Statistic	.053
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal.	
b. Calculated from data.	

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 3 it can be seen that the value of *asymptotic Significance* (2-tailed) is 0.200 > 0.05 thus based on the test criteria it can be concluded that the distribution of data has a normal distribution.

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity is a situation of correlation of independent variables between one and the other. It is said that there is no multicollinearity if a count > a and VIF, where: The amount of tolerance value (a) = 1 / VIF, The amount of variance inflation factor (VIF) = 1 / A. By using the amount of tolerance (a) and variance inflation factor (VIF) if using Alpha/tolerance = 10% or 0.1 then VIF = 10.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistic		
	Tolerance	VIF	Decision
Price (X1)	0,472	2.118	Multicollinearity Free
Citra Merek (X2)	0,312	3.201	Multicollinearity Free
Beliefs (X3)	0,347	2.878	Multicollinearity Free

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 4 multicollinearity test results show that the value of *tolerance* in each variable is greater than 0.1 while the value of *variance inflation factor* (VIF) variable price 2,118 < 10, brand image 3,201 < 10 and confidence 2,878 < 10 so that the regression model in this study does not contain multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The presence or absence of heteroscedasticity, in this study using a scatterplot test to plot the value of zpred (predictive value) with SRESID (residual value). The following heteroscedasticity test results using the help of IBM SPSS 25 are as follows :

Figure 1. Grafik Scatterplot

Source: SPSS 25, 2022

Based on Figure 1 results heteroscedasticity test results indicatekan bahwa scatterplot graph points *scatterplots* pread with an unclear pattern and below 0 at point Y so it can be concluded that in this regression model does not occur heteroscedasticity so that the model becomes feasible to predict every variables of this study.

The method of Data analysis in this study is descriptive analisisstatistical analysis, this analysis is shown to describe and describe the data from independent variables such as price, brand image and trust. This researcheruses a likert scale which is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena, the variables to be measured are determined to be variable indicators and then these indicators are used as a benchmark in preparing the questions. Here is the Likert scale:

Table 5. Variable Measurement Scale

Answer	score
Strongly Agree (SS)	5
Agree (S)	4
Fairly Agree (CS)	3
Disagree (TS)	2
Strongly Disagree (STS)	1

Source: Sugiyono (2017:93)

Based on Table 5 is used to calculate the score and the average value (*mean*). The following formula is used in order to determine the length of the interval class :

$$I = \frac{skt - skr}{V}$$

Further research using multiple Linear regression analysis according to Sinambela (2014: 217) multiple linear regression discusses the relationship of the dependent variable with two or more independent variables. Sugiyono (2014:

292) states that the regression equation can be used to predict how high the value of the dependent variable is when the value of the independent variable is manipulated (changed). Multiple correlation analysis according to Sugiyono (2017: 262), multiple correlation (*multiple correlation*) is a number that shows the direction and strength of the relationship between two independent variables together or more with one dependent variable. So that the formula can be used as follows :

$$r_{\mathbf{XiY}} = \frac{\mathbf{n} \sum \mathbf{XiY} - (\sum \mathbf{Xi})(\sum \mathbf{Y})}{\sqrt{\{\mathbf{n} \sum \mathbf{Xi}^2 - (\sum \mathbf{Xi})^2\}\{\mathbf{n} \sum \mathbf{Y}^2 - (\sum \mathbf{Y})^2\}}}$$

Based on the correlation analysis formula, it will obtain the value of r which is between -1.0 to 1. This notation uses the correlation or relationship between the variables tested in the study.

Analysis of the coefficient of determination (R^2) Atmaja (2014:122), states that the coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to see the extent to which the overall independent variable can explain the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. If R^2 is close to 1, the independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable. In other words, the smaller value of R^2 means that the ability of independent variables in explaining the dependent variable is very limited. The coefficient of determination can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\mathbf{KD} = \mathbf{r}^2 \times 100\%$$

A hypothesis test is an assumption about the relationship between variables in the population to be tested through the relationship between variables in the sample taken from the population (Sugiyono, 2016:224).

F Test (Simultaneous)

The F test is a significant test of the equation used to determine how much influence the independent variables together against the dependent variable (Sujarweni 2015:162).

T test (Partial)

According to Sujarweni (2015: 161), the T test is an individual partial regression coefficient test used to determine whether the independent variable (X) individually affects the dependent variable (Y).

RESULTS

Consumer Characteristics

Based on the description of consumer characteristics of Yamaha Mio Arista Tajur in the amount of 100 people who were sampled in the study, the following recapitulation of consumers of Yamaha Mio Arista Tajur:

Table 6. Recapitulation of Consumer Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Characteristics Consumer	Characteristics Consumer	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	59	59
2	Age	26-35 years	82	82
3	Level of Education	SMA/SMK	68	68
4	Employment	Of Private Employees	65	65
5	Monthly Income	Rp 3,000,000-Rp 5,000,000	47	47

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 6 above, it can be concluded that most consumers of Yamaha Mio Arista Tajur are male, aged 26-35 years, high school/vocational education level, private employee employment and income of Rp 3,000,000-Rp 5,000,000.

Recapitulation of consumer responses to price variables :

It can be seen that the recapitulation of consumer responses on price has an average rating of 3.76 including the appropriate category. The highest score value is equal to 4.26 and there is a Yamaha Mio motor indicator in accordance with its benefits when used has the lowest score value of 3.40.

Recapitulation Of Consumer Responses To Brand Image Variables :

It can be seen that the recapitulation of consumer responses to brand image variables for indicators of brand identity, brand association, brand behavior and Brand Excellence has an average Ror rating of 3.80. The brand identity indicator is the highest value getting a value of 4.38, which means that the value is in a good category. As for the lowest value obtained by the brand association indicator with the statement Yamaha Mio motorcycle is very classy and luxurious impression has a value of 3.40.

Recapitulation of consumer responses to the trust variable :

It can be seen that the results of the recapitulation of consumer responses to variable trust for integrity, goodness and competence indicators have an average value of 3.75, which means that trust is included in the good category. The indicator with the highest value with a value score equal to 3.92 and belongs to the good category. The indicator of information provided about the product in accordance with the promised specifications has the lowest score of 3.52.

Recapitulation of consumer responses to consumer satisfaction :

It can be seen that the recapitulation of consumer responses on consumer satisfaction has an average of 3.78 including the high category. The highest score value is equal to 4.00 on the indicator Produk given in accordance with expectations, while the lowest score value is equal to 3.58.

Multiple Correlation Analysis

To see the correlation between the variables can be seen in the following table:

Table 7. Calculation of Multiple Correlation and Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.759 ^a	.576	.563	2.00526
a. Predictors: (Constant), Trust, Price, Brand Image				
b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Satisfaction				

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Based on Table 7 above can be seen from the calculation can be obtained R-value or correlation of 0.759. According to (Sugiyono, 2017: 184) that the value of the interval is in the category of strong and positive (0.60-0.799).

Coefficient of Determination (R Square)

The coefficient of determination (R Square) can be used to determine the amount of contribution or contributions from all independent variables (X_1 , X_2 and X_3) the effect on the dependent variable (Y).

Based on the results obtained by the largest R square 0.576 or 57.6%. This shows that the percentage of contribution of the variable influence of Price, brand image, and consumer confidence on the Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur is 57.6% while the remaining 42.4%.

Simultaneous Regression Model Testing (F-Test)

Ho: $\beta_i \leq 0$: Price, brand image, and trust simultaneously do not have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction with Yamaha Mio motorcycles in Arista Tajur.

Ha: $\beta_i > 0$: Price, brand image, and trust simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction with Yamaha Mio motorcycles in Arista Tajur.

To test the statistical hypothesis is used F test statistics obtained through the analysis Table 8 of variance (ANOVA) as follows:

Table 8. Regression Coefficient Test Results Simultaneously

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	524.977	3	174.992	43.519	.000 ^b
	Residual	386.023	96	4.021		
	Total	911.000	99			
a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Konsumen						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Trust, Price, Brand Image						
Source: processed Data, 2022						

Based on Table 8 above that f_{count} of 43.519 while the F_{table} needs to be calculated using the significant degree of $\alpha = 0.05$ and degrees of freedom f ($k : n-k$) or $3 : 97$ ($100-3$) = 2.698. By looking at the results of the degrees of freedom then get the value of F_{table} of 2.698 so that $f_{count} > F_{table}$ ($43.519 > 2.698$) and has a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted meaning that price (X_1), brand image (X_2) and trust (X_3) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction on Yamaha Mio motorcycles in Arista Tajur.

Partial Regression Model testing (T-test)

T test was conducted to determine how the influence of price variables (X_1), brand image (X_2) and trust (X_3) partially affect consumer satisfaction (Y) on the Yamaha Mio motorcycle in Arista Tajur, it can be seen from Table 4.24 the value of t_{count} and significant value of each independent variable. While the value of the table t for $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $n-k-1$ or $100-3-1 = 96$ is equal to 1.661, the following results are obtained:

Tabel 9. T Test Result Table

		Coefficients ^a	
	Model	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2,344,021	.021
	Price	3.759	.000
	3,759,000 Brand Image	2,250. 0.250	.003
	Trust	4,377,000	.000

Source: Processed Data, 2022

Effect of price on consumer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur

It can be seen that the calculated t on the price variable (X_1) of 3.759 is greater than the table t value of 1.661 ($3.759 > 1.661$) and a significant value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). So thus H_{A1} is accepted H_{01} is rejected which means that partially the price (X_1) has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction (Y) there is a Yamaha Mio motorcycle in Arista Tajur. The test of one party for the price variable can be seen in the following figure :

Figure 2. Variable t Test Price (X_1)

Source: Processed Data, 2022

The influence of brand image on consumer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur

It can be seen that the calculated t on the brand image variable (X_2) of 2.250 is greater than the table t value of 1.661 ($2.250 > 1.661$) and a significant value of 0.003 is smaller than 0.05 ($0.003 < 0.05$). Thus H_{A1} is accepted H_{01} is rejected which means that partially the brand image (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction (Y) on Yamaha Mio motorcycles in Arista Tajur. The one-party test for brand image variables can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 3. Variable t Test (X_2)
 Source: Processed Data, 2022

The effect of trust on customer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur

It can be seen that the calculated t of the confidence variable (X_3) is 4.377 greater than the table t value of 1.661 ($4.377 > 1.661$) and the significant value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Thus H_{A1} is accepted H_{01} is rejected that partially Trust (X_3) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction (Y) on motor Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur. The one-party test for the confidence variable can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 4. Trust Variable t Test (X_3)
 Source: Processed Data, 2022

From the test results, a partial test recapitulation is made, namely price variables (X_1), brand image (X_2) and trust (X_3) as follows:

Table 10. Partial Recapitulation of the Test

No	Variabel	t _{hitung}	t _{tabel}	Sig.	A	Decision	Conclusion
1.	Price	3,759	1,661	0,000	0,05	Ha ₁ Received	Price has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
2.	Brand Image	2,250	1,661	0,003	0,05	Ha ₂ Received	Brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
3.	Trust	4,377	1,661	0,000	0,05	Ha ₃ Received	Trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

Source: Processed Data, 2022

According to Maja and Subdis (2012: 56) state that to determine the dominant independent variable influence on the dependent variable is used *standardized Coefficient Beta*. With this, the confidence variable (x_3) is dominant in its influence on consumer satisfaction (Y). this can be evidenced in the magnitude of the value of *the standardized Coefficient Beta* for the trust variable (X_3) is equal to 0.493 where the value is the largest value compared to the value of *the standardized Coefficient Beta* for the price variable (X_1) of 0.363 and brand image (X_2) of 0.030.

DISCUSSION

The price regression coefficient is positive, which means that every increase in the price variable (X_1) will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) for Yamaha Mio motorbikes at Arista Tajur assuming the brand image variables (X_2) and trust (X_3) are fixed.

The brand image regression coefficient (X_2) is positive, which means that every increase in the brand image variable (X_2) will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) for Yamaha Mio motorbikes at Arista Tajur with the variable price assumption (X_1) and trust (X_3) fixed.

The regression coefficient of trust (X_3) is positive, which means that every increase in the trust variable (X_3) will be followed by an increase in consumer satisfaction (Y) for Yamaha Mio motorbikes at Arista Tajur assuming the price variables (X_1) and brand image (X_2) remain constant.

Based on the regression agreement, it can be seen that price (X_1), brand image (X_2) and trust (X_3) have positive values. These results are in accordance with research conducted by Marlina & Masfufah Soebintaro (2021) which states that price, brand image, and trust have a positive influence on consumer satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Consumer response to the price, brand image, and confidence in consumer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur, it can be concluded that:
 - a. The average consumer assessment of the price (X_1) on the Yamaha Mio Di Arista Tajur belongs to the appropriate category.
 - b. The average assessment of brand image (X_2) on Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur is included in the good category.
 - c. The average rating of confidence (X_3) on the Yamaha Mio Di Arista Tajur is included in the good category.
 - d. The average rating of customer satisfaction (Y) on Yamaha Mio di Arista is included in the high category.
2. Price, brand image, and trust simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur
3. Price, brand image, and trust partially showed a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction at Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur.

FURTHER STUDY

The suggestions that researchers provide based on this study are as follows:

1. Based on consumer responses to the price it was found instrument with the lowest research is Yamaha Mio motorcycle in accordance with its benefits. Therefore, the company should improve the quality of the product in accordance with its benefits, such as the management of engine features on Yamaha Mio motorcycles.
2. Based on consumer responses to the Citra brand, it was found that the instrument with the lowest research, namely the Yamaha Mio motorcycle, was very classy and seemed luxurious. Therefore, the company should improve the existing features of the product so that it looks classy and futuristic, as well as updating *the design model* that is more elegant and attractive on the Yamaha Mio motorcycle so that consumers feel luxurious when using the motorcycle.
3. Based on consumer responses to trust, there is an instrumen with the lowest assessment, namely the information provided about the product in accordance with the promised specifications. Slike the information at the beginning of each purchase of a motorcycle unit will get one helmet and jacket, then the company must see whether the goods are available or not. Because after all, consumers still have the rightto get the goods as promised at the beginning.
4. Berbased on consumer responses terconsumer satisfaction on Yamaha Mio then there are instrumen with the lowest assessment that will make Yamaha Arista Tajur as the first choice for the purchase of two-wheeled vehicles. This should require an increase in the qualityof the products made by the company with tUjuan so that consumers feel satisfied.
5. For further researchers can make this study as a reference and reference. Further researchers are advised to look for other variables that affect consumer satisfaction Yamaha Mio in Arista Tajur in addition to price, brand

image, and trust in order to memeproleh more varied results and influence on consumer satisfaction to get a significantly greater value.

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